

Studies on Mixed Liquid Crystal. Part-I. Nematic Mesophase induced by Mixing Two Non-liquid Crystalline Components and Determination of Latent Transition Temperature

A V DOSHI* and N N JOSHI

Department of Chemistry, Matushri Virbaima Mahila College, Rajkot-360 001

Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 4 January 1993, accepted 18 March 1993

Eight binary systems consisting of both non-liquid crystalline components, viz. *p*-methoxyphenyl-*p*'-methoxy benzoate and Schiff base have been studied. One of the eight binary systems involving Schiff base *p*-tolual-*p*-phenetidine was found to give monotropic nematic liquid crystalline phase within definite range of concentration and temperature. Binary system involving *p*-anisal-*p*-phenetidine also gave monotropic nematic liquid crystalline phase as *p*-anisal-*p*-phenetidine itself is a monotropic nematic component. Moreover LTTs for constituent components determined by extrapolation method support the earlier work.

Binary systems in which one or both components are non-liquid crystalline were studied by different workers¹⁻⁸.

Mixed liquid crystal formation within definite range of concentration was observed in some binary systems of the type under present investigation. Eight binary systems comprising *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*'-methoxybenzoate and Schiff bases listed in Table 1 have been studied.

TABLE I-*p*-METHOXYPHENYL-*p*'-METHOXY BENZOATE
SCHIFF BASE

Compd no	$(p)R-C_6H_4CH=N-C_6H_4-R'(p)$			M p °C
	R	R'	T p °C	
1	OCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	(121.5)	128.5
2	OCl ₃	OCH ₃	-	147.0
3	N(CH ₃) ₂	OCH ₃	-	140.0
4	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	-	121.5
5	Cl	COCH ₃	-	133.0
6	Cl	Cl	-	112.0
7	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	-	108.5
8	Cl	Br	-	125.5

Results and Discussion

Among the binary systems (Table 1), the systems involving R = OCH₃, R' = OC₂H₅ and R = CH₃; R' = OC₂H₅ Schiff bases exhibited mixed liquid crystal formation over a range of 30.0–100.0 and 37.5–80.9 mole percent of the respective Schiff bases. Rest of the Schiff bases do not form mixed liquid crystals in their binary systems at any concentration. The transition curves of both the binary systems under discussion were extrapolated to zero and 100.0 mole percent of Schiff bases so as to determine LTT of constituent components. LTT of *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*'-methoxybenzoate was also determined by mixing it with a liquid crystalline component *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*'-methoxycinnamate⁹ to confirm results obtained in the present study. The extrapolation values for LTT of both the Schiff bases are studied by admixture of the individual components with a liquid crystal substance, *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*'-methoxycinnamate.

The tendency of non-liquid crystalline substance to form mixed liquid crystals is related to the polarity of the terminal groups present in the mole-

cule^{4,7,8}. Another component admixed with Schiff bases, i.e. *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*''-methoxybenzoate is a common component in all the binary systems. Moreover a central group -CH=N- in Schiff bases is also a common one. Therefore mixed liquid crystal formation can be directly correlate with the polarity of the terminal groups present in the molecule of Schiff bases. The polarity of OCH₃ group is greater than the polarity of CH₃ group⁷. As OC₂H₅ terminal group is contained by both the Schiff bases, i.e. Schiff bases 1 and 7 (Table 1), they differ only in their left terminals which are OCH₃ and CH₃ respectively. Therefore due to higher polarity of OCH₃, the extent of mixed liquid crystal formation in terms of mole percent in CH₃O-C₆H₄-CH=N-C₆H₄-OC₂H₅ is larger than that of CH₃-C₆H₄-CH=N-C₆H₄-OC₂H₅ which is evident from Figs.1 and 2. This fact is further evident from binary systems of Schiff bases 1 and 7 (Table 1) separately with a liquid crystal component *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*''-methoxycinnamate in Figs. 4 and 5. Overall polarity of the molecular and related cohesive forces involved in both the binary systems involving *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*''-methoxybenzoate as one of the components are such that statistically favourable parallel alignments of the molecular long axes in mixed melt occur and hence monotropic nematic liquid crystal formation occurs. Thus extent of mixed liquid crystal formation in terms of mole percent is attributed to the difference in magnitude of polarity of OCH₃ and CH₃ respectively. Thus the present study supports the polarity concept of terminal group in mixed liquid crystal formation.

Latent transition temperatures as determined by extrapolation (Figs.1-5) method, compare well with the previous work^{5,8}(Table 2.). Thus from the present investigation, evidence has emerged that lends credibility to the extrapolation method of predicting LTT.

Fig. 1 *p*-Anisole-*p*-phenetidine : *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*''-methoxybenzoate system : (O) solid-isotropic and (□) isotropic-nematic.

Fig. 2 *p*-Tolual-*p*-phenetidine : *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*''-methoxybenzoate system : (O) solid-isotropic and (□) isotropic-nematic.

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing equimolar proportion of aldehyde and amine in ethanol on a water-bath.

TABLE 2-COMPARISON OF LTT

Substance	Latent transition temperature (°C)						
	Fig 1	Fig 2	Fig 3	Fig 4	Fig 5	Ref 5	Ref 8
CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -CH=N-C ₆ H ₄ -OC ₂ H ₅	121.5	-	-	121.5	-	121.0	120.0
CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -CH=N-C ₆ H ₄ -OC ₂ H ₅	-	86.5	-	-	90.0	-	-
CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -COO-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃	80.0	81.5	80.0	-	-	-	-

Fig. 3 *p*-Methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxycinnamate : *p*-methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxybenzoate system : (O) solid-isotropic or solid-nematic and (□) isotropic-nematic or nematic-isotropic.

Fig. 4 *p*-Methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxycinnamate : *p*-anisol-*p*-phenetidine system : (O) solid-mesomorphic (nematic) or solid-isotropic and (□) nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic.

p-Methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxybenzoate⁹ : It was synthesised by heating *p*-anisic acid (1.6 g) with freshly distilled excess of thionyl chloride (2.4 ml) on a water-bath for ~ 2 h. The acid chloride so formed was directly treated with *p*-hydroxyanisole in pyridine, after complete removal of excess thionyl chloride. Reaction mixture was warmed in a water-bath with constant shaking for 45–60 min and kept overnight. The product was then treated with cold

Fig. 5 *p*-Methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxycinnamate : *p*-tolual-*p*-phenetidine system : (O) solid-mesomorphic (nematic) or solid-isotropic and (□) nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic

dilute HCl, filtered, washed with water, dilute NaOH and water and crystallised from alcohol (m.p. 125°).

p-Methoxyphenyl *p''*-methoxycinnamate⁹ : It was prepared by reacting *trans*-*p*-methoxycinnamoyl chloride with *p*-hydroxyanisole by similar method as described above (m.p. 117.0° : t.p.141.5°).

The binary mixtures were prepared by the usual method and transition temperatures of the samples were carefully observed⁶⁻⁸.

References

1. A. BOGOJAWLENSKY and N. WINOGRADOW, *Z Phys Chem*, 1907, **60**, 433, 1908. **64**, 229
2. R. WALTER, *Ber Dtsch Chem Ges.*, 1925, **58**, 2303
3. J. M. LOHAR, Ph.D. Thesis, M. S. University of Baroda, 1961
4. M. J. S. DEWAR and R. S. GOLDBERG, *J Am Chem Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 1582.
5. J. M. LOHAR and D. S. SHAH, *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst*, 1973, **28**, 293
6. A. V. DOSHI, Ph.D. Thesis, Saurashtra University, 1987
7. J. S. DAVE and M. J. S. DEWAR, (a) *J Chem Soc.*, 1954, 4617; (b) 1955, 4305.
8. J. S. DAVE and J. M. LOHAR, (a) *Proc Nat Acad Sci., India, Sect A*, 1960, **29**, 35; (b) 1960, 260. 1962, **32**, 105, (c) *Chem Ind (London)*, 1960, 567; (d) *Indian J Chem*, 1966, **4**, 386; (e) *J Chem Soc.*, 1967, 1473
9. J. S. DAVE, JR., Ph.D. Thesis, Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, 1980

